

PPI prediction from sequences via transfer learning on balanced but yet biased datasets: an open problem

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Abstract. Computational approaches for Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) prediction, and particularly, methods that predict interactions by leveraging only amino acid sequences are of paramount interest. In this study, we aimed to evaluate the suitability of pre-trained protein sequence embeddings, namely ProtBert and SeqVec, as feature extractors for classical machine learning algorithms. Consistent with recent reports, we found that performance metrics calculated over random train-test splits of balanced PPIs datasets, such as holdout or cross-validation, lead to highly overestimated values, mainly due to a non-evident bias present in such datasets. We demonstrate this bias by using two PPIs datasets and conducting a 5-fold cross-validation, which yields relatively high values for most tested models, including a custom baseline model, named PPIIBM, which predicts the interaction status based only on the a priori positivity of proteins found in the train split only. This baseline PPIIBM model achieves results similar to state of the art models, even of those based on deep learning, showing that predicting PPIs from sequences remains an open challenge, where careful validation pipelines should be implemented. Code available at <https://github.com/sing-group/ppi-ml>

Keywords: Protein-Protein interaction prediction, Sequence embedding, Sequential Data Analysis, Data Leakage, Machine Learning, Language Modeling, Deep Learning.

I. Hyperparameter tuning of machine learning models

Table S1. Hyperparameters used in inner cross validation (CV), and combinations of each iteration of outer 5-fold CV used to estimate the performance of machine learning (ML) models

ML Model	Parameter grid
k-nearest neighbors (kNN)	'n_neighbors': [25, 75, 125]
Logistic regression (LR)	'C': [0.0001, 1, 10], 'penalty': ['l1', 'l2']
Random forest (RF)	'n_estimators': [100, 200], 'min_samples_leaf': [1, 10, 50], 'max_samples': [0.75, 1.0]
C-Support Vector Classification (SVC)	'kernel': ['linear', 'rbf'], 'C': [0.0001, 1, 10], 'gamma': [1, 10, 100]

II. Evaluation metrics

In this article, for a given set of binary predictions, where a 2x2 confusion matrix can be computed, several evaluation metrics are presented, including recall, specificity, precision, accuracy, F1-score, and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), which provide a comprehensive insight into their applicability and usefulness in model classification evaluation. We define the metrics as follows:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{P}$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{N}$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{P + N}$$

$$\text{F1 - score} = \frac{2x \text{ Precision} * \text{ Recall}}{\text{ Precision} + \text{ Recall}}$$

$$\text{MCC} = \frac{TP * TN - FP * FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP) * (TP + FN) * (TN + FP) * (TN + FN)}}$$

where TP , TN , FP , FN , P and N represent true positive, true negative, false positive, false negative, real positive and real negative counts, respectively.

III. Dataset bias analysis

Figure S1. Distribution of the positive and negative protein interactions in Wei's dataset. Each point is a protein.

Table S2. Metrics (recall, precision, F1-score, accuracy, specificity, Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC)) obtained after training the different machine learning (ML) models, as well as the PPIIBM_{sim} model (predictions are based only on the positivity of the first item), and the PPIIBM_{bim} (predictions are based on the positivity of both items; see Pair Prediction by Item Identification Baseline Model (PPIIBM) and other machine learning models training and validation scheme), for the Wei’s dataset and using SeqVec as a pre-trained model for different combinations: concatenate (Concat.), concatenation combination plus inverse pairing augmentation (Concat.+inv), addition (Add), and multiply of embeddings.

Combination	Model	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	MCC
Concat.	PPIIBM _{sim}	0.616	0.954	0.749	0.793	0.971	0.628
	PPIIBM _{bim}	0.805	0.959	0.875	0.885	0.966	0.781
	kNN	0.782	0.852	0.815	0.823	0.864	0.648
	LR	0.848	0.867	0.857	0.859	0.87	0.718
	RF	0.892	0.89	0.891	0.891	0.89	0.782
	SVC	0.989	0.663	0.794	0.744	0.498	0.559
Concat.+inv (with augmentation)	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.812	0.867	0.839	0.844	0.875	0.689
	LR	0.854	0.871	0.863	0.864	0.874	0.728
	RF	0.899	0.896	0.898	0.897	0.896	0.795
	SVC	0.986	0.691	0.812	0.772	0.559	0.602
Add	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.796	0.874	0.833	0.841	0.885	0.684
	LR	0.855	0.869	0.862	0.863	0.871	0.726
	RF	0.852	0.871	0.861	0.863	0.873	0.725
	SVC	0.987	0.689	0.812	0.771	0.556	0.601
Multiply	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.707	0.821	0.76	0.777	0.846	0.559
	LR	0.825	0.833	0.829	0.829	0.834	0.659
	RF	0.855	0.852	0.853	0.853	0.851	0.706
	SVC	0.883	0.86	0.871	0.869	0.856	0.739

Table S3. Metrics (recall, precision, F1-score, accuracy, specificity, Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC)) obtained after training the different machine learning (ML) models, as well as the PPIIBM_{sim} model (predictions are based only on the positivity of the first item), and the PPIIBM_{bim} (predictions are based on the positivity of both items; see Pair Prediction by Item Identification Baseline Model (PPIIBM) and other machine learning models training and validation scheme), for the Wei’s dataset and using ProtBert as a pre-trained model for different combinations: concatenate (Concat.), concatenation combination plus inverse pairing augmentation (Concat.+inv), addition (Add), and multiply of embeddings.

Combination	Model	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	MCC
Concat.	PPIIBM _{sim}	0.615	0.953	0.747	0.792	0.970	0.625
	PPIIBM _{bim}	0.805	0.958	0.875	0.885	0.965	0.779
	kNN	0.831	0.845	0.838	0.839	0.848	0.679
	LR	0.851	0.872	0.861	0.863	0.875	0.726
	RF	0.882	0.905	0.894	0.895	0.908	0.790
	SVC	0.891	0.897	0.894	0.894	0.897	0.788
Concat.+inv (with augmentation)	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.843	0.864	0.853	0.855	0.867	0.710
	LR	0.857	0.879	0.868	0.869	0.882	0.739
	RF	0.898	0.912	0.905	0.906	0.913	0.811
	SVC	0.902	0.909	0.905	0.906	0.909	0.812
Add	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.823	0.878	0.850	0.854	0.886	0.710
	LR	0.857	0.882	0.869	0.871	0.886	0.743
	RF	0.847	0.897	0.871	0.875	0.903	0.751
	SVC	0.904	0.904	0.904	0.904	0.904	0.808
Multiply	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.765	0.799	0.782	0.787	0.808	0.574
	LR	0.808	0.824	0.816	0.818	0.827	0.635
	RF	0.848	0.894	0.870	0.874	0.899	0.748
	SVC	0.843	0.866	0.855	0.857	0.870	0.714

Table S4. Metrics (recall, precision, F1-score, accuracy, specificity, Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC)) obtained after training the different machine learning (ML) models, as well as the PPIIBM_{sim} model (predictions are based only on the positivity of the first item), and the PPIIBM_{bim} (predictions are based on the positivity of both items; see Pair Prediction by Item Identification Baseline Model (PPIIBM) and other machine learning models training and validation scheme), for the Yeast dataset and using SeqVec as a pre-trained model for different combinations: concatenate (Concat.), concatenation combination plus inverse pairing augmentation (Concat.+inv), addition (Add), and multiply of embeddings.

Combination	Model	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	MCC
Concat.	PPIIBM _{sim}	0.704	0.672	0.688	0.680	0.657	0.361
	PPIIBM _{bim}	0.807	0.828	0.817	0.820	0.832	0.640
	kNN	0.663	0.629	0.645	0.636	0.609	0.272
	LR	0.742	0.703	0.722	0.714	0.686	0.429
	RF	0.809	0.715	0.759	0.743	0.678	0.491
	SVC	0.615	0.625	0.620	0.623	0.631	0.246
Concat.+inv (with augmentation)	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.676	0.645	0.660	0.652	0.627	0.304
	LR	0.750	0.713	0.731	0.724	0.699	0.449
	RF	0.855	0.732	0.789	0.771	0.688	0.550
	SVC	0.664	0.630	0.646	0.637	0.610	0.274
Add	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.663	0.623	0.642	0.631	0.598	0.262
	LR	0.750	0.712	0.730	0.723	0.696	0.447
	RF	0.726	0.632	0.676	0.652	0.578	0.307
	SVC	0.674	0.623	0.648	0.633	0.592	0.267
Multiply	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.620	0.561	0.589	0.568	0.516	0.137
	LR	0.656	0.618	0.636	0.625	0.594	0.250
	RF	0.712	0.620	0.663	0.638	0.564	0.279
	SVC	0.674	0.624	0.648	0.634	0.594	0.269

Table S5. Metrics (recall, precision, F1-score, accuracy, specificity, Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC)) obtained after training the different machine learning (ML) models, as well as the PPIIBM_{sim} model (predictions are based only on the positivity of the first item), and the PPIIBM_{bim} (predictions are based on the positivity of both items; see Pair Prediction by Item Identification Baseline Model (PPIIBM) and other machine learning models training and validation scheme), for the Yeast dataset and using ProtBert as a pre-trained model for different combinations: concatenate (Concat.), concatenation combination plus inverse pairing augmentation (Concat.+inv), addition (Add), and multiply of embeddings.

Combination	Model	Recall	Precision	F1-score	Accuracy	Specificity	MCC
Concat.	PPIIBM _{sim}	0.704	0.673	0.688	0.681	0.657	0.362
	PPIIBM _{bim}	0.807	0.828	0.817	0.820	0.832	0.639
	kNN	0.688	0.610	0.647	0.624	0.560	0.251
	LR	0.728	0.690	0.708	0.700	0.673	0.401
	RF	0.805	0.739	0.770	0.760	0.715	0.522
	SVC	0.702	0.691	0.697	0.694	0.686	0.388
Concat.+inv (with augmentation)	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.696	0.627	0.660	0.641	0.586	0.283
	LR	0.738	0.701	0.719	0.711	0.685	0.424
	RF	0.846	0.754	0.797	0.785	0.724	0.575
Add	SVC	0.723	0.713	0.718	0.716	0.709	0.432
	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.671	0.608	0.638	0.619	0.566	0.239
	LR	0.738	0.701	0.719	0.711	0.685	0.423
Multiply	RF	0.697	0.650	0.673	0.661	0.625	0.323
	SVC	0.698	0.688	0.693	0.691	0.684	0.382
	PPIIBM _{sim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	PPIIBM _{bim}	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	kNN	0.641	0.554	0.594	0.562	0.483	0.125
	LR	0.660	0.608	0.633	0.617	0.575	0.236
Multiply	RF	0.703	0.652	0.677	0.664	0.626	0.329
	SVC	0.711	0.592	0.646	0.611	0.510	0.226